

DATA CENTER LOAD BALANCING UNDER HOMOMORPHIC ENCRYPTION

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Data Confidentiality must always be considered in applications of Data Science, such as cloud based AI-as-a-Service (AIaaS). This is widely recognized in the case of private data about individuals. Similarly a business must be careful with what business sensitive information it shares with the cloud, as it can provide market advantages to competitors if leaked. However, AIaaS can provide great value, and therefore a number of technologies that enable privacy preserving data science has emerged recently, such as hardware trusted execution environments¹ Alternatively, a software based technology like Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE) can provide very strong cryptographic guaranties². It permits computation to be performed by a public key holder, while the original data and results (both intermediate and final) can only be revealed by the private key holder. FHE has advanced from theory to application in the last decade.

This report describes work in progress that investigates the use of FHE technologies for a Data Center business set-up, where server cluster owners benefit from a cloud based AI service without revealing data about their operations.

Use case. We assume a grouping of data center operators (Clusters), for example organised as a franchise, that shares a central party (Broker) for distributing jobs from client applications. The optimal job assignment depends on the available resources in each of the clusters. This is a complex analytical task that involves prediction of future cluster states and compute requests, and we therefore assume that the group of clusters have employed a third-party service provider that owns an AI based algorithm with superior performance (the AIaaS). The algorithm is proprietary and can not be deployed at the customer site (i.e. any of the clusters), but is instead offered as a service in the cloud running under FHE. This set-up, which is illustrated in the Figure, preserves both the confidentiality of the cluster operational data and of the proprietary model.

Technical challenge. The AI based analysis residing in the cloud takes operational data like the current load distribution, idling server and server CPU temperatures as input to predict the optimal placement. A recent model³ that combines time-series modeling with random forests and neural network components, is simplified to allow

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¹S. Peisert. Trustworthy scientific computing, Communications of the ACM, Vol.: 64, No. 5, 2021.

²C. Gentry. Computing Arbitrary Functions of Encrypted Data, Communications of the ACM, Vol. 53 No. 3, 2010

³Desu et al. Latency-Aware Dynamic Server and Cooling Capacity Provisioner for Data Centers, ACM Symposium on Cloud Computing 2021

Figure. The broker distributes jobs within a grouping of processing clusters based on analytics provided by the AIaaS. Data flows between components are enumerated in the order they occur (with homomorphic encryption indicated by the star symbol).

an implementation that can run under FHE. This is a non-trivial task as FHE programming does not have regular flow control statements (if-then-else and do-while), and requires execution times orders of magnitude longer than for the corresponding plaintext program.

Work in progress. The work examines an algorithm that completes a single round of job assignment as follows: The Broker distributes FHE public keys (1) in the form of unique encrypted zeros to each of the Clusters, who uses it to encrypt their operations data and send (2) it to the AIaaS, which concatenates it to the encrypted job data it has received from the Broker (0). The assignment determined by the AI based analysis is (3) sent to the Broker, who then decrypts it and (4) notifies the selected Cluster.

An evaluation of different FHE frameworks concluded that as the AIaaS is stateful and contains non-linear components, the TFHE scheme as implemented in the Concrete library for Rust is most suitable for the application. The work is progressing to implement individual model components in the FHE software library with the target to run experiments for the integrated system on an actual cluster set-up. Preliminary results point to a feasible solution based on exponentially weighted moving average model, decision trees and job assignment by the homomorphic argmin operation.